

Significance of Golden Ratio And The Fibonacci sequence in Mathematics

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Abstract :

The discoveries of Leonard of Pisa, better known as Fibonacci, are revolutionary contributions to the mathematical world. His best-known work is the Fibonacci sequence, in which each new number is the sum of the two numbers preceding it. When various operations and manipulations are performed on the numbers of this sequence, beautiful and incredible patterns begin to emerge. The numbers from this sequence are manifested throughout nature in the forms and designs of many plants and animals and have also been reproduced in various manners in art, architecture, and music. . The golden ratio or the divine ratio has been applied in many works, whether artistic or in the field of architecture and medicine, and it is a mathematical theory that measures the proportionality between two elements within the design so that the value of this ratio is “1.618”, where a lot of research has been done to trace the roots of the emergence of the golden ratio where it was found in Nature, including the spiral arrangement of leaves and other plant parts or the shape of tornadoes.

Keyword: Fibonacci, mathematical world, Golden Ratio

Introduction: The mathematician Leonardo of Pisa, better known as Fibonacci, had a significant impact on mathematics. His contributions to mathematics have intrigued and inspired people through the centuries to delve more deeply into the mathematical world. He is best known for the sequence of numbers bearing his name. This thesis both examines more deeply the life and contributions of Fibonacci and depicts how his famous sequence is realized in nature, art, music, and architecture. As the thirteenth century began, Europe started to awaken from the Dark Ages and move into the Renaissance. As the stifling effects of the Dark Ages began to be replaced by a growing interest in the scientific world, artists, scholars, architects, scientists, and mathematicians all began making revolutionary discoveries and advances in knowledge. One such person was Leonardo of Pisa, who contributed to the transformation of the mathematical world at that time. Proportionality is a concept that refers to the importance of the relationships between the parts of the same geometric shapes in terms of a mathematical ratio, which is represented here by the golden ratio, concept of golden ratios and their relationships with basic geometric shapes through mathematical relations represented in the Fibonacci sequence and its applications in architecture throughout the ages through the use of the deductive approach and then the use of the inductive approach in order to find a mathematical technique that helps architects achieve golden proportions in their architectural designs through find an architectural module (grid) that achieves the Fibonacci sequence and thus achieves the golden ratios in the form of the relationship between the sides of the architectural spaces. Researchers have been interested in studying the architectural applications of the golden ratio, especially in ancient civilizations, where many theories emerged about the construction of the Great Pyramid in Giza (around 2570 BC) and the ancient Egyptian architect's use of the golden ratio in building the Great Pyramid (Meisner, 2016). In the twentieth century modernist architecture, artists and architects used the golden ratio, including Le Corbusier and Mies van der Rohe, where we find, for example, that Le Corbusier created a mule based on the Fibonacci sequence and the Vitruvian Man by Leonardo da Vinci to alternate his design with the golden ratio, especially the use of the golden rectangle, where the ratio of the longer side to the shorter side is the golden ratio (Livio, 2008).

The Fibonacci sequence:

Leonardo Bonacci or Leonardo of Pisa (1170- 1250) was an Italian mathematician from the Republic of Pisa, who discovered a sequence now known as the Fibonacci sequence that approximated the golden ratio, Fibonacci sequence is “a sequence of numbers in which each number is the sum of the previous two numbers: 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, etc. (Benavoli et al., 2009).

The Fibonacci sequence can be represented in the following simplified mathematical formula, which is the value of the simplest continuous fractions, which is $1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{1 + \dots}}}$ (Benavoli et al., 2009).

the series of Fibonacci sequence 1, 1, 2,3, 5, 8, 13... Source: The relationship of the golden ratio with the Fibonacci sequence can be found by dividing each number by the one before it.

- 1/1=1
- 2/1=2
- 3/2=1.5
- 5/3 = 1.666
- 13/8 = 1.625
- 21/13=1.615

The further you go in the series of Fibonacci sequence the closer you get to the golden ratio, for example: $377/233 = 1.61805$

(The simplest is the series of Fibonacci series)

Where $\Phi = x/y$ refers to golden ratio, (Φ) is the capital Greek letter Phi, the equation becomes,

$$\varphi = 1 + \frac{1}{\varphi}$$

Or equivalently Φ is the positive root of the quadratic equation:

$$\varphi^2 - \varphi - 1 = 0$$

The result of applying the quadratic formula is: $\varphi = \frac{\sqrt{5+1}}{2} \sim 1.618$

The negative root of the quadratic equation represents the conjugate golden ratio and is called \emptyset in relation to the lowercase Greek letter phi and is represented by the following equation:

$$\varphi = \frac{\sqrt{5+1}}{2} \sim 0.618$$

The relationship between the golden ratios sequence 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, etc.

The golden rectangle:

The golden rectangle is a rectangle of ratio between its sides that represents the golden ratio, where the golden rectangle is represented by drawing a square and then drawing a line from the midpoint on one side to the corner of the opposite side, then drawing an arc from the corner to the length of the side with the midpoint. conjugate ϕ and the golden ratio Φ , is given by, $\phi = \Phi - 1$

or using, $\phi = \frac{1}{\Phi}$

The relationship between the golden ratio conjugate ϕ and the golden ratio Φ . Source in the below fig.

Spiraling squares:

Spiraling squares: the full rectangle and the adjacent rectangle are both golden rectangles where the side is increased by the mathematical equation $\phi = \Phi - 1 = 1/\Phi$, to create a golden rectangle of length $L = \Phi$ and width $W = 1$, a smaller rectangle is attached to the unit square as shown in the figure 8. The smaller rectangle has a vertical length $L = 1$ and a horizontal width $W = \Phi - 1$, but since $\Phi - 1 = 1/\Phi$, the smaller rectangle satisfies $\Phi = L/W$, so it is also a golden rectangle (Hashemiparast & Hashemiparast, 2011).

This smaller golden rectangle can be divided again into a smaller square and a golden rectangle, and this process can continue infinitely, since in each subsection the length of the square is reduced by a factor of $\phi = 1/\Phi$. Subdivisions can be done either counterclockwise or clockwise, since in a clockwise direction, the square is placed first on the left, then up, then right, then down the rectangle, and so on. In the end, we get Figure 8, where the lengths of the sides of some squares in their centers are written as powers of ϕ .

Finally, a golden rectangle can be obtained as shown in Figure since it is a miniature version of the whole, and things that contain miniature copies of it are called similar.

Spiraling squares

The golden spiral:

The golden spiral is a special case of a logarithmic spiral of radius r which can be formulated

by the mathematical equation $r = ae^{b\theta}$ where θ is the usual polar angle, and a & b are constant values, since Jacob Bernoulli (1655-1705) carefully studied this spiral and gave it the name spiral mirabilis, or miracle spiral, then recommended that it be drawn on his tombstone with the inscription "Eadem mutata resurgo". Since the golden spiral is a logarithmic spiral whose radius increases or decreases by a factor of the golden ratio Φ with each quarter of a turn, that is, when it increases by $\pi/2$, where the golden spiral can be represented by the following mathematical equation: $r = a\varphi^{\frac{2\theta}{\pi}}$

The spiral can be formed inside the golden rectangle, the size of each successive square decreases by a factor of Φ , with four squares that make up each full turn of the spiral, then we put the center point of the spiral at the point of intersection of all squares, and fit the modulus a so that the golden spiral passes through the corresponding corners of the squares, then the Beautiful golden spiral shows as a result,

The golden angle:

The sunflower is represented as a reference from nature to measure the golden angles, where the golden angle is defined as the acute angle g that divides the circumference of the circle into arcs with a length in the golden ratio. The golden ratio Φ and the golden ratio conjugate φ satisfy: $\varphi = \frac{x}{y}$, $\varphi = \frac{y}{x}$ With $\Phi = 1 + \varphi$. We can determine the golden angle by writing $\frac{g}{\pi} = \frac{y}{x+y} = \frac{\varphi}{\varphi+1}$
 $= \frac{\varphi}{\varphi} = \varphi^2$ And since $\varphi^2 = 1 - \varphi$, we obtain $g = 2\pi(1 - \varphi)$,

The center of the golden rectangles and the golden spiral. is shown in the below fig.

Spiral center and Golden Rectangles AE The Golden Angle

= $AB = 1$, $AD = \Phi$, $FC(\emptyset) = \Phi - 1 = 1/\Phi$. Source

Golden ratio (Fibonacci sequence) in nature: Through studies that focused on the applications of golden ratios and successive Fibonacci in nature, he found, for example, the sunflower shown below in Figure, and noticed the spirals visible in the florets that radiate from the center to the edge, where we find that these spirals rotate in a clockwise direction and others in the counterclockwise.

By counting them, he found that 34 spirals are counterclockwise and 21 spirals are clockwise.

Surprisingly, the numbers 34 and 21 are Fibonacci sequence (Jozsef, 2016). The pinecone from the top, your eye will pick up spirals, there are actually two sets of spirals in this picture: 13 clockwise and 8 counterclockwise Here some Example uses of Fibonacci series and Golden Ratio ,also given the example of greek temple and pyramid uses of golden ratio its given below Applications of golden ratio in Architectural in Ancient Egypt:

In front of the studies that were carried out on the applications of the golden proportions in the field of architecture, especially ancient civilizations, it was found that one of the most important achievements of the ancient Egyptian civilization was the pyramid of Khufu, which came remarkably close to the "golden pyramid", as it was found that

The flowering head of a sunflower. The famous Greek temple, the Parthenon. Source Pyramid

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